

The significant roles of human resource Management Policy Implementation on the Employees Performance in the Public Universities in South Sudan: A Case of University of Juba (UOJ)

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Abstract

The study's goal was to look at the roles of human resource management policy implementation and performance in South Sudanese public universities, namely the University of Juba. A total of 100 populations were included in the study, with an 80-person sample size. Employees were chosen using a stratified random sampling method. Data was collected using a standardized questionnaire that has been verified. Inferential and descriptive. This study achieved its main goal using a mixed methodological approach that combined qualitative research with quantitative approaches to describe the target. Using the SPSS statistical tool for social research, the data was processed and shown in tables with frequencies and percentages, as well as graphs. According to the study's findings, there is a relationship between the application of Human Resource policies and performance. The University of Juba should hire people based on their competency, according to the findings of this study. It was also revealed that the University does not provide training to its staff on every new technology that is introduced. The study concluded that the importance of HRM policy implementation has critical effects on the performance of public universities, and that HRM practices should be carried out in the most efficient and effective manner for maximum performance in the university industry. It is important to note that HRM policies have a high degree of positive influence on universities that can produce success and positive result for the sector. It was suggested that the University of Juba's administration award and acknowledge its employees in order to inspire them and make them happy in their jobs.

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Introduction

The overall goal of this research is to look at the impact of Human Resource Management Policy Implementation on employee performance in South Sudan's public universities. It is based on a University of Juba case study (UOJ). The study looks at how policies are implemented. It is assumed that the management of the policy implementation process has a direct impact on the attainment of the policy's goals, which is the study's purpose. The study is significant because effective human resource strategies must be implemented in public colleges. The University of Juba (UOJ) in South Sudan was the region's first public university, founded in 1975 following the Addis Ababa Peace Agreement in 1972, when the city was still part of Sudan. The University of Upper Nile in Malakal, which is now based in Juba owing to the continuing civil conflict, Rumbek University, the University of Bar EL-Ghazal, and Dr. John Garang Memorial University in Bor were the other four public universities in South Sudan as of April 2014. The university has returned to Juba, where it was founded, following the independence of South Sudan in July 2011. The university's instructions are given in English. Human Resource Policy Implementation and Management is defined by Bramham (2008) as the process by which management determines how to take the organization from its present manpower situation to its intended position. Management aims to have the appropriate amount and types of people in the right locations at the right time, doing the right tasks, so that both the company and the individual profit in the long term.

According to Schneider et al., (2000), policy implementation management requires assistance in ensuring that workers have the skills and competences that the company need to succeed. Human Resource Management collaborates with the organization strategy to determine the resources required to meet the company's objectives. It will better prepare management for employee attrition, recruiting, and strategic hiring, as well as reduce stress in the event of an emergency or last-minute hiring need. The competence model is most effective, according to Dubois et al (2015), when everyone in the targeted categorization understands which abilities the agency considers important to successful job performance. The Competence Model's terminology will become knitted into the fabric of the company and integrated into employee performance if it is utilized regularly. According to Robbins et al (2015), performance refers to how successfully or poorly individuals accomplish their job responsibilities. Effort and talent are two factors that influence performance. A manager's instructions can either assist or impede performance. Though salaries and compensation influence the value of labor, simply paying employees a regular rate may not be enough to inspire them to go above and beyond the bare minimum. According to the University of Juba's performance report (2010), the university provides incentives to workers, such as training in the form of scholarships and workshops, to encourage them to improve their skills and effort, therefore boosting performance. Human Resource Management's objectives, according to the University of Juba's Human Resource Management policy (2012), are to establish norms, guidelines, and measures that will enable the University to select the number and quality of employees with the necessary competencies to meet the organization's current and future needs.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the University of Juba's efforts to educate and manage its workforce through human resource policy, there have been several concerns about employee recruitment, training, and compensation. According to a 2008 international audit study on the Human Resource Management Directorate at the University of Juba, the university had a high employee turnover rate of 34% at the end of 2008. In that year, 56 percent of the workforce was hired, but 33 percent of the employees left. The average length of service for the personnel was two years, much too short for the University to reap the benefits of its investment and training.

Staff morale has been negatively affected primarily because of salaries that were below market rate for quiet, resulting in staff turnover; appraisal and exit interviews revealed that some employees felt their efforts were not appreciated or adequately rewarded; staff training was not structured, preventing optimal performance. University of Juba lacked enough employees, and religious affiliations other than those recognized by the university remained a problem, exposing the institution to inefficiencies and, in the end, poor services. According to the University of Juba's annual performance report from 2009, the university was on the edge of failure on many times until the South Sudanese government decided to reorganize the university's management as a condition for saving the learning institution. The authority blames the University's recurrent failures on its inept and incompetent administration. As a result, the University's Human Resource policy implementation and management team has recently been confronted with the task of obtaining, maintaining, and developing highly skilled and capable employees in order to restore the University's glory and bring it up to world-class standards. According to the annual performance report of the University of Juba (2015), Admiration devotes a significant amount of effort on operational matters. They hire for today's requirements. They are unconcerned about future requirements. As a result, they consider Human Resource Management procedures to be a nuisance. It also criticizes the whole management structure for delegating most Human Resource Management procedures to line managers, despite the fact that they are not professionals, experts, or knowledgeable enough to take on the job. He goes on to say that senior management and an incentive structure should be established to motivate them, something that does not exist in South Sudan's state colleges. As a result, the research intended to evaluate the relevance of Human Resource Policy implementation and performance in South Sudanese Public Universities, with a focus on the University of Juba.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The survey revealed the gaps in the literature on the University of Juba, which the current study aims to fill. The literature study looked at the models that researchers have used to explain the impact of human resource policy implementation on employee performance at both public and private institutions in general. This chapter discusses the study's relevant topics. The relevance of Human Resource Management Policy implementation on employee performance at Public Universities was studied, and it was based on a case study of Juba University.

Literature Survey

According to Gregory et al. (2014), a research on the application of Human Resource management policies in various firms revealed that these institutions matched their parent companies' recruiting policies. However, unlike with parent corporations, where direct contact with educational institutions is established and interviews may be performed on campuses, this practice is not as extensive. There are various differences in Malaysian businesses' recruiting methods when compared to Japanese firms' recruitment processes.

According to the author's observations and experiences, full-time local employees in South Sudan are mostly recruited through newspaper advertisements and walk-in interviews, while others are hired based on who you know rather than professional processes. In certain situations, recruitment/selection is based on the advice of family and close friends. In another case study, Abdullah et al. (2015) found that vacant jobs in the Ugandan electronics industry are first given to existing employed personnel. Performance and seniority are used to evaluate qualified applications. When there are several applicants with equal qualifications, seniority is utilized as the deciding factor. If this technique fails, employees are circularized in the hopes of finding someone appropriate among their friends or family. After then, the position would be posted outside the firm. Surprisingly, the firm thinks that this approach enhances the family's

ability to analyze the influence of recruiting and selection on performance, necessitating the necessity for this study.

Another significant element of Juba University's Human Resource Management Policy Implementation on Employees [Academic Staff] is full employee engagement. Universities in the United States of America [USA] have created different types of organizational learning mechanisms, such as the suggestion system, to continually improve the process of quality control at the academic level in order to generate a Quality Assurance. He went on to say that because of the emphasis on cross-departmental coordination and collaboration, it's critical for businesses to promote multifunctional abilities so that employees may learn cross-functional skills and collaborate to achieve organizational goals. Job rotation is a continual activity that helps to build strong and successful work teams, which are essential for improving product quality and organizational effectiveness. The study focused on how staff training and development improves organizational effectiveness, but it did not go into detail on the training techniques utilized or how they affect the organization's overall performance, necessitating this study.

Broader Area of Inquiry

The impact of Human Resource Management policies on employee performance is not limited to the University of Juba. It has not been a subject of research by many scholars elsewhere in organizations in similar environments, therefore some of the models that have arisen are examined below, as well as this study, which has potential for comprehending the difficulties brought at the University of Juba. The process of selecting a subset of potential applicants for employment is known as selection (Muchinsky, 2005). The objective of selection activities is to match individuals to occupations and guarantee that future work performance is at the highest level possible (Arnold, et al, 2007). Choosing the appropriate individuals for the right job is critical to any organization's long-term performance and profitability (Opra, 1998)⁵, referenced by Mwesigwa (2005). According to studies, the best selection techniques are those that closely match the content of the job being considered, according to Opra. Unfortunately, many recruiting consultants are ignorant of the low success rates associated with some of the processes they promote. Poor selection, according to Dubois et al. (2006). They claim that issues arise when applicants who would have performed well are rejected and those who perform poorly are eventually admitted. The expenses of educating the employee, the revenues lost as a result of the individual's ineptitude, the cost of severance, and the following costs of recruitment and selection screening. They recommend that the main goal of any selection activity be to minimize the likelihood of making reject or accept errors while increasing the likelihood of making accurate judgments.

Competency-based recruitment, according to Robbins et al. (2014), is a recruitment process based on candidates' ability to produce anecdotes about their professional experience that may be used as evidence that the candidate has a certain competency. Candidates exhibit their abilities on the application form and then during the interview, which is referred to as a competency-based interview in this situation. By clearly laying out the required competencies and then testing them in such a way that the recruiter has little discretion to favor one candidate over another, the process is intended to be more fair than other recruitment processes. The process also assumes that high recruiter discretion is undesirable. The approach is popular in government because of its apparent fairness; competence-based recruiting places a strong emphasis on a candidate's ability to tell a narrative as an indicator of competency, while ignoring other indicators of a candidate's talents and potential, such as references. A competence model is a set of skills that are necessary for a certain profession. According to Gruber (2010), recruitment and selection are used to forecast the applicants'

prospective job performance. Organizations may use this technique to discover the finest people to assist them achieve their goals. Traditional and competency-based recruiting and selection vary in that the latter places a greater emphasis on formal, quantifiable capabilities. When Competency Modeling is backed by Ontology, it can be more successful. Ontology is a type of semantic technology that is used to define ideas of phenomena and the relationships between them.

Figure 2.1: Integrated competency Model

Source: Dubois et al, (2008)

Consistency is important when applying the competence model; using one set of competencies for the selection process and another for performance management encourages misunderstanding and undercuts the competency model's efficacy. Furthermore, the competence model will be most effective if everyone in the targeted categorization of the business understands the abilities the agency considers essential for successful job performance. The Competence Model's terminology will become knitted into the fabric of the company and integrated into employee performance if it is utilized regularly. Competency, according to the OntpHR project (2011), is a temporally stable, clearly defined, and trainable capacity to effectively execute an organizationally valued prospective work task. Competency models for a job position or an entire institution should be developed in order to profit from competencies. When comparing the competency base model supplied by Dubois et al, (2015) to that of HR project, the one provided by Dubois is extremely significant since it fits well in the culture of University of Juba, given that the whole process used here is the same method used by University of Juba management. Employee training, according to Thomas (1997), entails teaching employee's skills that will enable them to become more efficient and productive workers. Most jobs require some form of on-the-job training, and having a well-trained workforce provides advantages for both employees and employers. New workers are frequently given training to acquaint them with their jobs' tasks and responsibilities, as well as corporate rules. Many businesses provide staff with ongoing training opportunities, concentrating on skills that might help them be more efficient. Because they believe the firm has invested in their abilities and growth, well-trained employees frequently have better motivation and morale. As a result, there are less turnover rates. According to Armstrong

(2010), trained personnel generally perform better as a team since everyone is aware of the expectations and can achieve them in a coordinated manner. Employees who have received training are also more confident in their abilities to perform and make decisions. Employees that are trained on a regular basis are also more inclined to embrace change and come up with fresh ideas. Employees who receive training and gain new abilities are ideal candidates for promotions because they have demonstrated their capacity to absorb, retain, and apply information. Reliable competent workers can also be empowered to train other employees, easing the management team's workload. Because few people arrive at work with all of the information and experience necessary to execute their assigned job, training is meant to assist learners with the knowledge and skills they need for their current employment (Fitzgerald, 1999). Human investment not only offers competitive advantages for a company (Salas, et al, 2001), but also gives innovations and chances to learn new technologies and enhance employee skills, knowledge, and firm performance, according to Becker (1962). In reality, companies are becoming more conscious that investing in training may improve their performance in terms of higher sales and productivity, improved quality and market share, reduced turnover, absenteeism, and conflict. Training, on the other hand, has been attacked as faddish or excessively expensive, and there is growing doubt regarding its practice and theoretical underpinnings, as well as its relation to company success (Wright, et al, 2001). The effectiveness of an organization's Human Resources is critical to its success. As a result, every company must strive to enhance the quality of its workforce. Training is one method of attaining this. The significance of training can only be fully recognized if it has a direct influence on employee performance. An increase in employee performance leads to an increase in the performance of the company (Aduda, 2013). He claims that almost all employees have received some form of training. This is because training improves employee motivation, career opportunities, allows employees to take on greater responsibilities, increases commitment to work, and so on. Both senior managers and employees believe that training is important and should be enhanced further in order to have a workforce that can perform effectively.

Job factors, organizational features, and worker qualities all influence employee training. The disparities between employees who get formal training and those who do not were described by Black et al, (1999). Workers are more likely to receive training if their jobs have the following characteristics: cognitively complex jobs (e.g., professional, technical, and managerial jobs), customized products, high-value-added jobs with a lot of responsibility, and sales jobs for complicated, changing, and use expensive machinery on the job, regular, full-time jobs, non-temporary jobs, and jobs where the skills learned are not useful at many other firms in the community. While other worker attributes remain constant, the frequency and quantity of formal training received by employees in a given year is determined by the features of the occupations they hold, the business for which they work, and the people themselves. As a result, businesses often assess training requirements to decide where training is required and who needs to be trained. Guest (1987) established a theoretical framework to demonstrate how HRM policies influence human resource and organizational results. Gust's model has the advantage of being a useful analytical framework for evaluating the link between HRM policies and organizational performance since it is stated in routes that allow for more rigorous, unambiguous, and straightforward empirical testing. He regarded commitment as a viral consequence, concerned with the goals that bind employees to company performance, since the aim of quality is critical to ensuring high-quality products and services. As a result, training and development policies are important in HRM because they help to improve strategic integration, employee commitment, flexibility, and quality. HRM outcomes can lead to high job performance, high problem-solving activity, high cost effectiveness, low turnover, and fewer grievances. Wright et al. provide another theoretical paradigm that stresses the

interconnectedness and coherence of HR practices, company strategy, and firm level results (1992). Six theoretical models from organizational theory, finance, and economics are presented. The link between training and company performance is examined in three of them (resource-based view of the firm, cybernetic systems, and behavioral viewpoint). Kozlowski et al., (2000) provide a method to organizational reform and development focused on improving the workforce's knowledge, skills, attitudes, and capacities. Training activities may be used to achieve the paradigm. Training is successful in this context if it contributes directly to the strategy, objectives, or outcomes that are important to organizational effectiveness. Current models, on the other hand, do not effectively handle theoretical frameworks. This is a theoretical model that is offered in the hopes of aiding in the understanding of the link between training and firm performance. A theoretical framework was created and presented to add to the theoretical literature in order to meet the need for evaluating training and employee performance concerns. Figures 2.2 and 2.3 depict this structure. The essential foundations of training procedures, HR results, and organizational performance are based on Figure 2.2. Training is expected to help achieve greater levels of group and corporate goals, outcomes, and personnel performance. In the second and third boxes, a number of HR outcomes and company performance that are relevant in assessing the connection are included. Some of the most important factors are highlighted. Training has an impact on employees' total knowledge, skills, abilities, attitudes, behaviors, and motivation, as shown in Figure 2.2. Employee performance is directly influenced by HR results. Figure 2.2 shows a more sophisticated structure in which these techniques are linked to training and firm performance connections.

Figure 2.2: A framework for analyzing training and performance issues

Figure 2.3: Training, organizational (University) strategy and performance

Source: Kozlowski et al, (2000)

In the long term, aiming to improve HR outcomes will have a positive impact on employee performance (i.e. academic and nonacademic performance). To determine whether training

improves employee performance, academic performance, or non-academic performance, a process of HR outcomes and employee performance assessment must be considered together in real situations in order to reach a consensus on its meaning. In terms of the performance used in this model, a distinction can be made between academic institutions and non-academic institutions. In this topic, academic success is connected to metrics such as Quality Education (QE), whereas non-academic performance includes labor turnover, employee absenteeism, and conflict. It is critical to establish a check list that will be utilized consistently when reviewing employee performance. Every company's method for evaluating employee performance may be different. So far, the data suggests that there is a general opinion that there is a favorable link between training and employee performance. Thus, via the development of skills, knowledge, abilities, competences, and behavior, training has a beneficial influence on employee performance by creating advantages for both the individuals and the company they work for (Evans, 1999). On-the-job training is important for the growth of organizations, as it improves performance and productivity, placing them in the best possible position to confront competition and stay on top. This implies that there is a strong link between companies that teach their staff and those that do not (Evans, 20001). Compensation is a tool that owners may use to provide financial incentives for managers to reduce their opportunistic behavior; ideally, an employment contract would be created that set pay equal to the marginal output of labor. The profitability of a bank, on the other hand, is a result of both management effort and random variables outside the control of managers. As a result, determining effort just by looking at corporate earnings is not a flawless science. As a result of the problems connected with unanticipated circumstances and the principal-agent dilemma, writing employment contracts is tough (Jensen et al, 1990). According to Chen et al. (2003), "Incentive pay has a very significant premise that material and spiritual motivations should mix." Based on an examination of principle agent theory, this article concludes that the current application of material remuneration has resulted in a decrease in confidence between principal and agent. A study uses the complement to the principal-agent theory as an opportunity to introduce a psychological contract, which is designed to build long-term trust between principals and agents while reducing the agents' opportunistic behavior. It is also suggested that professional managers build spiritual remuneration on the basis of psychological contract theory, which obviously has more practical significance.

Figure 2.4: Integration model for incentive pay

Source: Chen, et al, (2003)

The above demonstrates that the compensation system based only on the agency theory has certain flaws when it comes to motivating their agents' actions. This is not to suggest, however,

that the hypothesis is incorrect. It can only demonstrate that the manager is a complex social figure whose new motivation cannot be understood only through the lens of agency theory. The manager's conduct will be significantly influenced by the psychological contract. Some researchers have begun to look at how agency theory and psychological contract theory may be combined. The paper provides an incentive pay integration model, in which material pay is created and based on the principal-agent theory, integrating professional managers' performance and providing material incentives. However, the psychological contract criteria, which are based on the principle of fairness, should be maintained. Simultaneously, psychological contract theory, as a complementarily to the principal agent theory, added that the building of complementarily to the principal and agent will not only throughout the entire idea of pay administration, but also to discover a genuine vector. It can be changed into spiritual remuneration to be built, and to realize the complementarily and integration of principal-agent theory and psychological contract theory in the construction of pay model, according to the organizational responsibility understood by employees as outlined in empirical analysis of psychological contract theory. However, according to Gunkel (2005), the Porter-Lawler model (1968) extends the Vroom expectation model (1964). He goes on to say that the motivation model is founded on the premise that workers act in a way that maximizes their utility. Employees are motivated, according to his premise, if they anticipate their performance to contribute to their pleasure, such as by raising their compensation. As a result, employees should perform better if their pay is linked to their performance rather than if they are paid a wage that is unrelated to their performance. According to Porter et al (2008), the value of incentives and remunerations, as well as the chance of receiving a reward, impacts an employee's efforts. Employees' characteristics and skills, as well as their perceptions of their positions within the business, are said to impact the link between performance and effort, according to their concept. Their approach recognizes that performance-based rewards are frequently not equivalent to the reward that employees believe they should receive. Greater levels of predicted incentives and remunerations are linked to higher levels of self-rated performance. The arrows below show the link between perceived rewards and performance. Employees are only satisfied when their compensation or awards meet or surpass their expectations.

Figure 2.5: Model on performance and perceived rewards

The Porter & Lawler model, according to Griffn et al. (2009), gives an intriguing insight into the connection between pleasure and performance. They go on to say that the expectation theory's initial presentations put it solidly in the mainstream of modern motivation theories. The majority of the changes, on the other hand, have been focused on identifying and measuring the objectives and expectations. They make an exception for Porter et al.'s version of expectation theory (2008). This concept, they claim, claims that if rewards are appropriate, high levels of performance can lead to contentment. Performance leads to two types of rewards: intrinsic rewards, which are intangible, such as a sense of accomplishment and accomplishment, and extrinsic rewards, which are tangible consequences such as money and promotions. In this circumstance, the employee assesses the worth of his work to the organization in order to create an opinion about the reward he has gotten. Employees are satisfied with their jobs when they believe their incentives are fair.

2.4.1 Defining Performance Appraisal

The systematic, frequent, and unbiased evaluation of an employee's proficiency in areas relating to his current work and his potential for a better position is known as performance appraisal. Flippo expanded on the notion of PA by defining it as a formal and systematic evaluation of an employee's work performance in comparison to specified criteria, as well as the communication of that evaluation to employees. Performance assessment, according to Fishar, Schoenfelt, and Shaw (2010), is the process of evaluating an employee's contribution to the business over a certain period of time. "All formal methods used to assess personalities, contributions, and positions of group members in a working organization are included in performance appraisal. It's a never-ending process of securing the data needed to make accurate and impartial choices on employees." - Yoder, Del (1998). "All formal methods used to assess personalities, contributions, and potentials of group members in a working organization are included in performance appraisal. It's a never-ending process of securing the data needed to make accurate and impartial choices on employees." Yoder, Dale (1998). The performance appraisal is a component of the performance management system, which is a broader system. This system is a method of motivating individuals to achieve their full potential by combining performance, planned goals and objectives, measurement, feedback, and acknowledgment. Setting explicit quantifiable goals and objectives, as well as evaluating individual performance against these metrics, are all part of performance evaluation. We may infer from the preceding definitions that performance assessment is a technique of assessing workers' conduct at work, which often includes both quantitative and qualitative elements of job performance. It is a method of analyzing both work-related behavior and employee potential that is methodical and objective. It is a procedure that entails determining and conveying to an employee how he or she is performing on the job, as well as, ideally, developing a plan for improvement. Individual growth is emphasized in performance evaluations. It is now used to assess the performance of all human resources, including technical, professional, and management employees, at all levels of the company.

METHODS OR TECHNIQUES OF PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL

Traditional Methods: These approaches are based on personal attributes like as knowledge, capacity, judgment, initiative, attitude, loyalty, and leadership, among others. The conventional techniques of performance evaluation are as follows:

Unstructured Method of Appraisal: The appraiser must explain his feelings regarding the employee when using this approach. This is a straightforward approach of evaluating employee performance. The rater must provide his views on the essay evaluation technique, critical incidents approach, straight ranking method, paired comparison method, and field review method in his comments.

Straight Ranking Method: The evaluator assigns relative ranks to all employees in the same work unit doing the same task using this approach. On the basis of overall performance, employees are graded from best to worst. This technique is also very subjective and unfair in determining an employee's true worth.

Paired Comparison Method: Employees in a group are compared to one another at the same time using this approach. This method compares each employee against all others in the group one at a time, which is a superior form of comparison than the straight ranking method.

The workers are given final ranks when all of the comparisons have been made on the basis of the overall comparisons.

Man-to-Man Comparison Method: Certain criteria are chosen for analysis using this approach. These traits include initiative, leadership, and so forth. For each factor, the appraiser creates a scale.

Grading Method: Certain categories of worth are decided in advance and are thoroughly specified using this approach of performance evaluation.

Graphic Rating Scale: The visual rating scale is the most often utilized technique of performance evaluation. The assessor is requested to assign a score to each employee based on work-related qualities and job expertise. This approach evaluates an employee's quality and quantity of work using a visual scale that indicates varying degrees of a certain attribute. Personal traits as well as attributes connected to employees' on-the-job performance are among the criteria taken into account. A feature like Job Knowledge, for example, can be graded on a scale of ordinary, above average, exceptional, or unsatisfactory.

Checklist Method: A checklist is a collection of objectives or descriptive statements regarding an employee's conduct in its most basic form. The rater examines each comment to determine if an employee's conduct is favorable or bad. A checklist containing descriptions of the workers' on-the-job behavior was provided to the rate. The checklist consists of a series of statements that the rater uses to describe the employees' on-the-job performance.

Weighted Checklist: The checklist provides statements relating to work-related behavior of the employees, where every statement is given equal importance.

Free Essay Method: There is no quantitative technique used in this procedure. It is a form of employee evaluation that is open-ended.

Critical Incidents Method: The worker's performance is graded using this approach depending on specific occurrences that occur during the course of the task (i.e. the evaluation is based on key incidents). The evaluator assesses the employee using this type of performance assessment based on significant events and how the employee acted during those occurrences. There are both bad and positive aspects to it. The disadvantage of this technique is that the supervisor must keep track of important occurrences and employee conduct as they happen.

Field Review Method: An HR professional interviews line supervisors to assess their subordinates using this approach. A senior member of the HR department or a training officer talks and interviews the supervisors in order to evaluate and grade their respective subordinates using this approach. This approach has a significant disadvantage in that it takes a long time to complete. However, this technique aids in reducing superiors' personal prejudice.

Confidential Reports: The immediate supervisor's secret report is nevertheless a substantial hindrance to the subordinate's advancement or transfer.

Modern Methods: Performance assessment approaches used now are superior than those used in the past. Modern techniques are an attempt to fix flaws in older methods. The following are examples of current approaches for evaluating employee performance: **Behaviorally**

Anchored Rating Scales (BARS): Its purpose is to discover a job's important areas of performance. The behaviorally anchored ratings scales are defined in this technique in order to detect the important regions of effective and poor performance behavior. BARS

(behaviorally anchored rating scales) are a novel methodology that combines the visual rating scale with the critical incidents method. It is made up of preset essential areas of job performance or sets of behavioral statements that rate significant job performance characteristics as excellent or negative (for e.g. The qualities like inter-personal relationships, adaptability and reliability, job knowledge etc.). Critical occurrences have led to the development of these statements. The actual job behavior of an employee is assessed against the planned conduct using this approach, which involves recording and comparing the behavior using BARS. Expert knowledge is required for developing and practicing BARS.

Result-oriented Appraisal or MBO technique: The concrete performance objectives, which are generally created collaboratively by the superior and subordinates, are the foundation of result-oriented evaluations. Management by Objectives is the name given to this method (MBO). Peter Drucker was the first to introduce the concept of Management by Objectives (MBO) (1954). It is a process in which workers and superiors come together to establish shared goals, the employees determine their own goals to be reached, the standards to be used as the criterion for measuring their performance and contribution, and the employees decide on the course of action to be done. MBO is defined by participatory goal-setting, action-planning, and decision-making. The measuring and comparison of the employee's actual performance to the specified criteria is an important element of the MBO. Employees are more likely to complete their tasks when they are involved in goal-setting and selecting the course of action to be taken. MBO provides goal clarity through the notion of SMART objectives, which are defined as goals that are Specific, Realistic, Achievable, Measurable, and Time constrained.

Human Resource Accounting Method: Any organization's human resources are a significant asset. This asset can be appraised in monetary terms. The human asset of a business is reduced when competent and well-trained workers depart, and vice versa. Every organization's human resources are significant assets. The approach of human resource accounting is to determine the relative value of these assets in terms of money. Employee performance is evaluated using this technique based on the cost and contribution of the employees. Employees' costs comprise all expenditures associated with them, such as remuneration, recruiting and selection charges, induction and training costs, and so on, whereas their contribution is the entire value provided (in monetary terms). The performance of the personnel will determine the difference between the cost and the contribution. Employee contribution should, in theory, be more than the expense of employing them.

Psychological Appraisals: These are used to evaluate an employee's performance. Employees' emotional stability, interpretation and judgment skills, sociability, intellectual talents, reasoning and analytical abilities, motivating reactions, and capacity to predict the future are all tested.

360 Degree Appraisal: It is a performance evaluation approach in which employees receive feedback from persons on all sides of them in the organization, including their supervisor, colleagues and peers, and their own subordinates. As a result, 360-degree feedback is received from all sides. Managers can benefit greatly from this type of performance review since it generally provides a far broader variety of performance-related input than a standard evaluation. 360 degree feedback, also known as "multi-rater feedback," is the most complete evaluation in which information regarding an employee's performance is gathered from all sources that interact with him on the job. This approach is widely utilized for performance evaluations across the world. Wipro, Infosys, and Reliance Industries are among the companies that are following it. The researcher employs this approach in his investigation and production of the Performance Appraisal Model.

Conceptual Framework

The purpose of the research was to determine the impact of Human Resource Management Policy Implementation on Employee Performance at the University of Juba. The literature review led to the development of the following conceptual framework.

Source: self-developed from literature review

A variety of variables have been recognized as contributing to the adoption of Human Resource policies. They are divided into three categories for the purposes of this study: selection procedures, training and development, and remunerations. While performance is the primary variable of interest, it is also the dependent variable, and the study's goal is to identify the reasons that cause variance at the University of Juba. In this study, the dependent variables will be evaluated in terms of productivity, quality, and satisfaction. It's worth noting that highly skilled personnel put in more effort, resulting in higher-quality work. South Sudan Statutory regulation powers, political interference, and personal interest are the intervening variables that influence the relationship between the independent variables (Significance of Human Resource Management Policy Implementation) and the dependent variable (Significance of Human Resource Management Policy Implementation) (performance). It should be emphasized that when statutory requirements are strictly followed, the importance of Human Resources Management is of high quality, which has a beneficial influence on the University of Juba Academic Staff's performance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The path via which researchers must perform their study is known as research methodology. It demonstrates how these researchers define their problem and aim, as well as how they present their findings based on the data collected throughout the study period. This chapter on research design and technique also explains how the final research result will be attained in accordance with the study's goal. As a result, the research methodologies utilized during the study process are discussed in this chapter. It covers the entire research process of the study, from the research plan through the dissemination of the findings. For emphasis, in this chapter, the author outlines the research strategy, research design, research methodology, the study area, sample size determination, data sources such as primary data sources and secondary data, population consideration and such as questionnaires Interview Guide Approach, and Observation sample size determination, workplace site exposure measurement sample determination, data collection methods like primary data collection methods including workplace site observation data collection and data collection through questionnaires, secondary data collection methods, data obtained from experts opinion, data collection through desk review, workplace site exposure measurement, data collection tools pretest,

methods of data analysis used such as quantitative data analysis and qualitative data analysis, data analysis software, the reliability and reliability of data, validity analysis of the quantitative data, reliability analysis, validity, data quality management, inclusion criteria, ethical consideration and dissemination of result and its utilization approaches. In order to meet the study's aims, both qualitative and quantitative research methods are recommended. Because the data were acquired from all elements of the data source during the study period, the study employed mixed methods. As a result, the goal of this approach is to fulfill the researcher's study strategy and objectives.

Data Analysis, Ethical Considerations and Data Processing

Table 4.1 Gender of respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	40	80
Female	10	20
Total	50	100

Source: Field data 2018

Background information of the Respondents

Figure (4.1) Gender of the respondents

Source: table 4.1

The results reveal that the bulk of the respondents (80%) were male and 20% were female, as shown in table 4.1 and figure 4.1. In terms of female respondents working in government institutions, this means that the percentage of male respondents is larger than that of female respondents. As a result, women must be upgraded to adult education and self-reliance training in order to meet male standards. This supports Lenders and Flynn's (2006) assertion that uneducated women lack the skills and knowledge necessary to achieve higher-paying occupations.

Table 4.2 Age of respondents

Age group	Frequency	Percentage
20 - 29	10	20
30 - 39	21	42
40 - 49	09	18
50 - 59	05	10
60 years and above	05	10
Total	50	100

Source: Field data 2018

Figure (4.2) Ages of the Respondents

Source: table 4.2

Figure 4.2 shows the age of the respondents; the results show that 18% of the respondents were between the ages of 40 and 49, (42%) were between the ages of 30 and 39, (20%) were between the ages of 20 and 29, (10%) were between the ages of 50 and 59, and only 10% were between the ages of 60 and above. This indicates that the majority of responders are between the ages of 40 and 49. (42 percent). The majority of responders are youthful and enthusiastic, indicating that they are willing to contribute their mental and physical efforts to the organization. This is supported by Migino's (1998) study, which found that active aging reflects many people's desire and ability to remain engaged in economically and socially productive activities, while the risks of chronic illness and disability rise or fall with age, implying that they have a direct relationship.

Table 4.3 Marital Status of the Respondents

Status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	40	80
Single	10	20
Divorced	00	00
Total	50	100

Source: Field data 2018

Figure (4.3) Marital Status of the Respondents

Source: table 4.3

The survey results reveal that (80%) of the respondents were married and (20%) of the respondents were single, as shown in figure (4.3). According to the findings, married respondents made up the largest number of participants (80%). Which implies that marriage

is a South Sudanese custom, and that if a girl kid reaches the age of 12, she must wonder why no one has asked for her hand?

Table 4.4 showing educational background of respondents

Qualification level	Frequency	Percentage
Diploma	02	04
Bachelor degree	22	44
Master's degree	19	38
Ph.D.	07	14
Total	50	100

Source: Field data 2018

Figure (4.4) Shows Education Background of the Respondents

Source: table 4.4

According to figure 4.4, 44% of participants were university bachelor certificate holders, 38% were master degree certificate holders, 4% were diploma certificate holders, and just 14% were Ph.D. holders. This demonstrates that the respondents have a strong ability to not only execute tasks but also to reply successfully to the questionnaires that have been supplied. This backs up Smithy's (2001) study, which found that an employee's educational level influences his or her capacity to do day-to-day tasks.

Table 4.5 Showing occupation of the Respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Human Resource Department	20	40
Department of Accounting	07	14
Procurement & Logistics	13	26
ICT Department	10	20
Total	50	100

Source: Field data 2018

Figure (4.5) Show occupation of the Respondents

Source: table 4.5

According to table 4.5, 40% of respondents work in the department of human resources, 26% in the department of procurement and logistics management, 20% in the department of information communication technology, and only 14% in the accounting sector of the department of accounting and finance. The bulk of the respondents in this example were employees in the human resource department, which is what the researcher is interested in.

Table 4.6 showing the criteria for selection of staff at the university

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	05	10
Strongly agree	04	08
Neutral	41	83
Total	50	100

Source: Field data 2018

Figure (4.6). Showing the criteria for selection of staff at the university

Source: primary data

Respondents were asked about the selection criteria used at the university in Figure 4.6, and the findings show that 10% of respondents agree with statements such as the university employs employees on the basis of competence, considers job specifications when hiring staff, follows a clear guideline when making selections, and shortlists candidates. Only 8% of respondents are unsure about the assertions, but the majority strongly agree with them. As a result, the majority of respondents believe that the above-mentioned standards are strictly observed because this is a learning institution.

Table 4.7 showing training of staff in the University

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	15	30
Strongly agree	05	10
Not sure	30	60
Total	50	100

Source: Field data 2018

Figure (4.7.) Showing training of staff in the University

Source: table 4.7

Respondents were asked about how the university trains its staff in the above figure 4.7, and based on the findings, the majority of respondents (60 percent) said they are unsure about statements like the university trains its staff on every new technology that is developed, the university encourages its staff to learn new skills, and university employees are equipped with new skills and the university invests more in staff training (30%) of the same number of respondents agree with the above mentioned claims as well, with just 10% of respondents strongly agreeing with the above mentioned statement. As a result, the majority of respondents agreed with the statement.

Table 4.8 showing remuneration of staff in the University

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	32	64
Strongly agree	11	22
Not sure	07	14
Total	50	100

Source: Field data 2018

Figure (4.8) showing remuneration of staff in the University

Source: table 4.8

The above figure 4.8 shows that the majority of respondents (64 percent) strongly disagree with the statements that the university provides fringe benefits to all its employees, employees of the university of Juba are adequately paid, employees of the university are motivated by not only paying them but also by recognition and praise, the university equitably pays staff, and the staff are rewarded in accordance with the university's policies. Only (14%) of respondents are uncertain about the claims, with 22% agreeing. As a result, the vast majority of respondents disagree with the claims on university employee salaries.

Table 4.9 showing the criteria considered when employing staff

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	05	10
No	45	90
Total	50	100

Source: Field data 2018

Figure (4.9) Showing criteria the University considered when employing staff

Source: table 4.9

Respondents were asked to give their opinions on what factors the university considers when hiring an employee, and the results show that the majority of respondents (88%) said the applicant's academic qualifications, that the university sometimes considers the employee's nomination, and that only 12% of respondents said the university considers the employee's salary. As a result, the question of whether colleges recruit people they know is ruled out.

Table 4.10 showing consideration of job Specification

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	15	30
No	35	70
Total	50	100

Source: Field data 2018

Figure (4.10.) Showing consideration of job Specification

Source: table 4.10

Respondents were asked whether the university considers job specifications when hiring staff, and the findings show that the majority of respondents (75%) said no, with only (25%) saying yes, confirming that job specifications are taken into account during the hiring process.

Table 4.11 showing whether or not short listed candidates are interviewed

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	35	70
No	15	30
Total	50	100

Source: Field data 2018

Figure (4.11.) Showing whether or not short listed candidates are interviewed

Source: table 4.11

Respondents were polled on whether or not the university interviews all short-listed candidates for jobs when hiring staff, and the results show that the majority of respondents (70%) say they interview all short-listed candidates, while just 30% say they interview only the selected candidates.

SUMMARY

The importance of Human Resource Management Policy implementation and performance at Public Universities was the subject of this study, which used the University as a case study (UOJ). When assessing this survey, a sample of 40 respondents was used. This research included both qualitative and quantitative methods. The questionnaire and the interview were the primary data collecting techniques. The data was analyzed using SPSS (statistical program for social science).

Selection of Employees: According to the findings of the study, the bank hires people based on their abilities. This means that the University of Juba's staff are qualified and skilled enough to carry out the university's functions. When asked what factors the university examines when hiring someone, it was revealed that the bank looks at the candidates' qualifications and skills before hiring them. It was also discovered that job requirements are taken into account while hiring personnel. This means that the bank takes the candidates' credentials and talents into account when hiring them for positions at the university. It was also found that some of the University of Juba's workers are relatives of the Deans, although the University of Juba prioritizes an individual's degree of credentials and skills. According to the findings of the survey, precise rules are followed while choosing candidates for the position. This suggests that the recruiting committee does not pick people based on the job description and specifications. Employee credentials and talents are taken into account, but no specific criteria have been established by the University of Juba for recruitment personnel to follow. According to the research, while picking candidates for a position, shortlisted candidates are taken into account. It was discovered that not all University of Juba personnel were questioned. They were selected for the position based on their resumes and application forms.

According to the findings of the study, the University of Juba hires professionals to choose employees for open positions. It was found that the recruitment officials handled them all similarly, and that they were all treated fairly. The survey showed that while hiring personnel, candidates' credentials and experiences are not taken into account. This means that the

University hires people based on their technical knowledge. When asked if the University hires people they know, it was discovered that the majority of the staff at the University of Juba are relatives of the Deans. Internal workers are chosen to fill the empty jobs, according to the findings of the research. This means that the University fills open jobs with people who are qualified and capable. When asked if all vacant jobs are filled by internal workers, the University of Juba stated that all open positions are filled by qualified and competent individuals, whether internal or foreign. According to the findings of the study, the University of Juba handles all of its candidates equally during the screening process. This means that applicants are evaluated based on the interview report, their applications and C.Vs, and their panel presentation. When asked how they were handled during interviews, candidates reported that varied inquiries were asked about their documents and resumes. According to the findings, the University of Juba hires successful candidates after conducting interviews. It was discovered that the University hires internal professionals to fill management vacancies. According to the results of the study, the University includes its Deans in the selecting process. This indicates that the University selects its personnel with the help of outside professionals. When asked if they were questioned by the same individuals who interview them at the University of Juba, they were told that the recruiting and selection process was handled by internal specialists.

Training of Employees: According to the conclusions of the survey, the University of Juba provides training to its staff on each new technology that emerges. This suggests that University workers lack the essential abilities to carry out their professional responsibilities and tasks. When asked if they are trained on every new technology, it was discovered that the University of Juba does not teach its staff on every new technology in order to equip them with the skills they need to execute their duties successfully. It was also disclosed that the bank's staff had been trained in the new abilities. This indicates that the university employs qualified personnel. When asked if the staff are trained on a regular basis, it was revealed that they are trained as needed. According to the findings, the university does not provide its staff with possibilities for advancement. This means that staff will be able to obtain additional training on their own. When asked if their training is paid for by the University of Juba, staff disclosed that they pay for their own education.

The bank encourages its workers to learn new skills, according to the conclusions of the research. This means that competent applicants will be rewarded handsomely at the University of Juba. When asked what incentives are offered to skilled employees, the respondents claimed that skilled employees have a better possibility of getting promoted and having more possibilities at the University of Juba. It was also disputed that skilled workers are not given the opportunity to instruct their coworkers. This means that skilled employees teach their coworkers how to use the abilities they have. When asked if they learn from their coworkers, it was discovered that the majority of the talents they have come from their coworkers. According to the conclusions of the survey, the University of Juba devotes greater resources to employee training. This means that the university pays for all of its workers' training. When asked if the university pays for their training, it was revealed that the University of Juba pays for all interested applicants' training in order to inspire them and improve their performance. Workers at the University of Juba are also urged to work in groups in order to recruit new employees, according to the report. This means that University of Juba workers work in groups. When asked if managers provide teamwork positions to their staff, it was found that the University of Juba does.

According to the findings of the study, on-the-job training is used at universities when training personnel. This means that the University of Juba provides hands-on training to its staff. When

asked if the University trains its workers off the job, it was discovered that University of Juba personnel receive both on and off-the-job training. It was also revealed that the University of Juba does not provide equal training to its workers. This means that the university educates a certain set of individuals. Employees of the University of Juba are taught on new procedures in the bank, according to a question about whether they are trained. According to the findings of the study, trained personnel are neither more motivated or have a higher morale than untrained ones. This means that awards and other motivators are used to inspire University of Juba personnel. When asked if they are motivated by training, they said that they are driven by par.

Remuneration of Employees: The University does not give fringe benefits to all of its workers, according to the conclusions of the research. This means that the University does not compensate employees for property and services if the value to the employees surpasses the expense to the employer. It was also discovered that the University of Juba provides its staff with vehicles, parking, food, and medical care. It should be mentioned that providing good fringe benefits to employees may enhance job satisfaction and enable employers to offer a competitive benefits package. According to the conclusions of the survey, University of Juba personnel are underpaid. This means that the University pays its workers according to their level of responsibility. The University of Juba has disclosed that their staffs are paid according to their employment level and position within the university. When it comes to awarding staff at the University of Juba, a pay roll is taken into account. Employees at the University of Juba are not only driven by prizes, but also by praise and recognition, according to the conclusions of the research. This suggests that income is the primary motivator for employees.

Employees at the University of Juba are dissatisfied with their salaries, according to the conclusions of the research. This suggests that staffs at the University of Juba are not motivated by their pay. According to the research, employees at the University of Juba are rewarded if they work according to the pay roll and are paid after three to four months. Employees at the University of Juba are not awarded allowances or fringe benefits for their achievements, according to the research. This means that University of Juba staffs are simply paid a salary and enjoy no further perks. It was also found that the staffs receive enough compensation, which makes them happy with their jobs. According to the conclusions of the investigation, the bank fairly compensates its staff. It was discovered that the bank pays its workers based on their job titles. It was also revealed that bank personnel are compensated based on the quality of their service. This means that the bank pays its workers based on the quality of service they provide. It was also discovered that the bank compensates staff for every good performance they provide. According to Armstrong (2011), there are two types of equity. The first is distributive equity, which is concerned with how individuals see their rewards in relation to their contributions and in contrast to others.

CONCLUSION

In earlier research, the importance of Human Resource management policy implementation in the business sector has been underlined. As a result, any concerns relating to the execution of Human Resource policies in any company sector must be investigated. The goal of this research is to look at the impact of Human Resource Management Policy on Public Universities at the University of Juba. The outcomes of this study show that staff selection, training, and compensation have an influence on work performance. This finding is in line with previous management literature on policy implementation in human resource management. Different questions are provided to the respondents and therefore analyzed in order to acquire more particular information of selection, training, and remunerations from the sample firms.

Employee involvement in selection, training, and payment for responders' work is the subject of these questions.

The results of the questions about employee participation in selection, training, and remuneration indicate that these companies have good and perhaps clear policies regarding training and development, as the majority of respondents indicated that they had participated in training and that they were provided with opportunities to train as part of the company's mandatory practice for all employees. When it comes to the topic of training program quality, the results show that the programs offered by the sample firms are relevant in the eyes of the respondents.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the summary findings and general survey conditions of the situation of human resource management policy implementation in public universities, the following policy recommendations could be used to improve human resource management policy implementation on employee performance in South Sudan's public universities. The government/Ministry of Higher Education should revitalize and develop an efficient framework for monitoring and evaluating the execution of human resource management policies. Effective and efficient training or capacity building for the Human Resource Department of the University of Juba's employees and officials. The government of South Sudan should provide financial and administrative assistance to both public and private universities, as well as other educational institutions in the nation, in order to improve service delivery. The processes for hiring academic and administrative personnel are accessible and should be followed in line with South Sudan's Ministry of Public Service and Human Resource Development's labor rules. With the help of the Ministry of Higher Education, the University of Juba's administration shall offer appropriate and effective training to both academic and general administration support employees. Finally, for greater results, the University of Juba and the Ministry should examine remunerations that please personnel. This can also be applied to other South Sudanese state universities.

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